

THE ROLE OF A TEACHER IN TEACHING PROCESS

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Annotation: This article discusses the main responsibilities of teaching, which is the noblest profession, the significance of teachers not only in education but also in the teaching process, their professional ethics, their responsibility for creating a positive learning environment, and their commitment to and accountability in that environment. Additionally, it explains what is being taught.

Key words: teacher, teaching process, traits, students, profession, professional ethics, knowledge transmission, educator, organizer, creator, adviser, certificate, motivator, commitment subject.

I discovered nine fundamental qualities of a good teacher before discussing the duties of a successful teacher. Four of these characteristics pertain to the personality of the teacher, while the remaining five concern their interactions with the pupils. Since I had begun my course, I had realized that I must put these qualities to use in order to be a successful teacher and have a significant impact on students' advancement.

A good teacher should be polite, patient, truly passionate about teaching, and capable of inspiring students, according to the first four personality-related factors. The other half of the paragraph explains that a teacher should be knowledgeable about the subject, able to establish relationships with pupils, and able to engage all of the class members. Additionally, a competent teacher should be able to gently correct students' errors without detracting from their motivation. He or she should also be able to identify the students' strong and weak points and know how to enhance their strong qualities and address their poor ones.

After considering these attributes, I believe that I should use them to set myself apart. Learning the many roles of teachers inside the classroom, how to switch between them depending on the circumstances and the students in the class, and the advantages of each position are the main benefits of the TEFL certification.

The supervisor. A teacher may play some or all of the following roles during a normal lesson: In the first function, known as the controller, teachers are in command of the group of students and the task in a way that differs significantly from when they are working independently.

The coordinator. Being an organizer is the second function. This is one of the most crucial roles since teachers often have to put students in groups or pairs to complete different tasks, give directions, start activities, end activities, and manage feedback. Teachers must feel at ease in this position because if the pupils are not informed of the assignment, pandemonium may result. Also, we should know about top five skills teachers need to set their students up for success.

Assessor. A third role is to act as an assessor; Sometimes students make English mistakes and the teacher will need to act as an assessor, providing feedback and correction as well as evaluation and grading. It is very important that the teacher deals fairly with all students and is very sensitive to students' reactions and provides necessary support.

The promoter. A fourth role is to explain how and when the teacher can act proactively. When students lose the thread of what they are trying to say or run out of ideas, the teacher decides whether to let the student work it out for himself or whether the teacher should gently encourage the student. The second option explains the role of a query. When prompting, the teacher should be careful not to take the initiative from the student. Therefore, great sensitivity and encouragement is required.

The participant The next role is when the teacher acts as a participant. At certain points in the lesson the teacher may wish to participate in the lesson as a peer rather than as a teacher. There could be a number of reasons for this, such as

being able to participate in activities with students or balancing the number of pairs in an activity. As a participating teacher; It is essential not to dominate the activity or draw attention to him/her.

People try to live a happy life while they are alive, so they try to create a promising life through studying, learning and teaching. We study, research and improve our skills in a particular field but we also know that in these endeavors we need a coach to provide us with basic education and skills. Teacher, Teaching - These are the words we come across when we start in any field, because we refer to the teacher in the biggest, most prestigious, highest paying fields and in some equally prestigious professions. Have we ever wondered what these words mean? What is a teacher or teaching? As Paula Coelho says, "I tell you that it is not someone who teaches something, but someone who inspires students to give her/his best to discover what she/he already knows". Some Internet sources describe teaching as follows: Teaching is the process of paying attention to people's needs, experiences, and feelings, to help them learn specific things and to go beyond what is given. Also, at www.igi-global.com engagement, publication, and the scholarship of teaching and learning, we can be sure that it has two foundations: teaching. There are two fundamentally different ways to understand teaching. The former views teaching as an instructor-centered activity that transmits knowledge to novice learners. Helping, guiding and encouraging novice learners and their active and independent new knowledge creation: Teaching as supportive knowledge creation. Besides, teaching is the profession of teacher, which helps a person to develop fully in body, mind, soul, intellectual feelings and moral values and artistic sensibility.

The teaching process is the purposeful transfer of knowledge, experience and skills from one person to another, with the teacher as the primary provider. Nowadays, in order to develop technology and increase the information, responsibilities and actions of the teaching profession, it is becoming more difficult and the demand for it is increasing, so it is considered noble. Respect the opinions

and attitudes of learners and students, create a good mood in the teaching process, have a positive attitude, demand skillfully from students who strive for their goals, be alert and attentive to everything, maintain their professional skills in any situation and constantly. Collaboration encourages the teacher to be unique.

We can point out nine characteristics of a great teacher, which are listed below:

1. A great teacher respects students' opinions.
2. A great teacher creates a sense of community and belonging in the classroom.
3. A great teacher is warm, approachable, enthusiastic and caring.
4. A great teacher sets high expectations for all students.
5. A great teacher has a passion for learning.
6. A great teacher is a great leader.
7. A great teacher is flexible.
8. A great teacher collaborates with colleagues on an ongoing basis
9. A great teacher maintains professionalism in all areas.

The teacher's role is not only in education, but also in how we respond to what happens around us, our duties and responsibilities and our role as educators. Also, as an organizer of the teaching process, that is, as a creator of learned lessons, teachers play the role of a psychologist who provides scientific guidance throughout the lesson and in situations where learners have to make a decision. If the students inside are highly motivated then the process of learning task will be successful. The teacher plays a crucial role in developing motivation and motivation in students in learning. Finding solutions to improve the quality of education is everyone's responsibility. This raises questions about education or teaching, its purpose and the teacher's role in the process.

To summarize, the great teacher profession played an important role in the teaching process because every simple or popular profession is achieved through a teacher. As mentioned above, we discussed the unique and noble teaching profession with its professional ethics, specifically, educator, facilitator, modeler, manager, mentor, motivator and creator of educational facilitation, as well as

Oakeshott's ideas and facts. On it. An inspired and knowledgeable teacher is the single most important school-related factor affecting student achievement, so it is critical that we pay close attention to how we train and support both our new and experienced educators. The best professional development is ongoing, experiential, collaborative, and engaging and derived from working with students and understanding their culture. Apart from them, a very important aspect of successful teaching is dedication. Dedicated teachers care about the development of their students. A commitment to continuous professional learning is an integral part of effective teaching. In short, for the teacher, every action and activity is a role in the teaching process.

They may be an actor, singer, psychologist or designer, but the most important thing is to teach the learners useful and accurate information and knowledge. If the teacher creates a warm, happy environment, students or students are more likely to be happy. The environment created by the teacher can be positive or negative. Students spend a lot of time with their teachers. If students perceive that the teacher is angry, students may react negatively to it and thus learning may be impaired. If they divert the environment, that is, increase their ownership of the classroom processor to listen to learners, this action increases students' confidence and sense of purpose.

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